

Brief information about diabetes

It is the condition that too much sugar present in blood stream. This cause damages to blood vessels and nerves. Diabetes is a non-transmitted disease, but the patient and take control of it via *treatment adherence* and self-management.

What is diabetes?

We need energy to live. Our body get energy from the food we eat. After eating, some food is broken into a type of sugar called, "Glucose" in our body. The body of person who has diabetes cannot use glucose correctly to give him or her energy. There are some health problems that can be caused by diabetes, such as, always feeling tired, not seeing well, losing weight even though you eat well, feeling very thirsty, frequent urination, itchiness of private parts, sexual dysfunction, and wounds that do not heal. Untreated diabetes, meaning too much glucose left in the body for a long time, can cause damages to fine nerves and small and large blood vessels. Diabetes is a non-transmitted disease, but the patient can take control of it via medication adherence and self-management.

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healthy food, regularly exercis
limit alcohol drinking